

Effects Of Recruitment and Selection on Academic Staff Performance at Nasarawa State University, Keffi – Nigeria - A Pilot Study

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Abstract

Academic staff performance amongst Nigerian lecturers is deteriorating year by year. This problem started a very long time ago and will be difficult to be separated from the possible issues having to do with poor staff recruitment and selection of academic staff by public universities of which Nasarawa state university is included. This is a pilot research conducted to test the validity and reliability - feasibility before the actual or full-scale research is carried out. SPSS Version 25 is used to test for validity and reliability of instruments which indicated that the Cronbach alpha is not less than 0.7 threshold and so it is fit for use in conducting full-scale research.

Keywords: *Recruitment, Selection, Academic, Performance and Staff.*

INTRODUCTION

Academic staff in Africa performed extremely well within the last 8-10 decade ago where most institutions recruit and retain qualified academic staff for better performance. This was achieved because of the affiliation of most institutions in Africa to British, French, Portuguese and other European institutions. The partnership enhanced the performance of academic staff because the European union countries introduced the quality assurance procedure which was observed in affiliated institutions. There were few institutions in Africa with few numbers of students which result to high performance because of the close supervision by management of the institution. Academic staff morale was high due to motivation, packages provided by the management. (Elijah 2016).

Nasarawa state university was established in 2002. At this period academic staffs were few because of the few departments existing, staff were privileged to be sent abroad for training. Promotions were done as at when due, staff were placed appropriately in their areas of specialization. This is because selection was done based on merit. This boosted the performance of the academic staff that made the students nickname the institution as the school of test and assignment. Students' practicals were carried out effectively. Quality research work by the students/academic staff, field trips were observed, this was so because of the motivation package given by the management.

Moreover despite the high performance by the academic staff, there are some setbacks which can be traced back as far as 1980s and 1990s where African states realized the need to have an educated masses in various fields of studies to support the economic growth and development of their countries, it was a time of increase in population more secondary schools established and more students yearning for higher education as a result the Government established more higher institutions by granting private individual license to established private schools absorb the teeming population of the secondary school students. Although the establishment of more institutions has increased opportunities for both parents and their children to access higher education. It is also a fact that weak students have joined the institution and their performance is not the best, Academic staff are overloaded with courses as a result of inadequate staffing or lack of

adequately trained one. Nevertheless, staffs are expected to be prepared for delivering lectures, mentor students and attend both local and international conferences so as to compete favorably, (Alemu 2010).

Although, the quest for more high institutions and massive enrolments of students with few equipments and academic staff is peculiar and more pronounce in African countries. However, in Nigeria specifically at Nasarawa state university, the magnitude of student enrolment in the institution with little number of academic staff is very high. Moreover, the university later has introduced new departments and more courses. The newly established departments and courses need more academic staff to handle it. Although, an advertisement was placed by the management requesting for suitable applicants to come and fill the existing vacancies, and of course majority of the applicants, applied for the job base on their areas of specialization. However, due to high rate of unemployment and corruption bedeviling recruitment process in Nigeria, most highly placed individuals in the societies have influenced the recruitment and the selection process. This has seriously affected the selection process because of the pressure mounted on the management. This has led to the extent that some departments had more than enough staff from same rank/cadre while other departments had few staff. Some Academic staffs were pair two to three to lecture a particular course while some were overloaded. Staff training was not done base on the need of the department but on who is in the good books of the management. Thereby making wrong placement that is not in line with their areas of specialization. This has caused a serious problem that affected the performance of majority of the academic staff in the institution. This has also led to the situation where some Academic staff found it very difficult to express themselves. Difficulties experience by academic staff in expressing himself implies phobia for crowd, and cannot impact knowledge to the students effectively.

However, it is assumed that proper recruitment and selection played a very significant role on academic staff performance, this was justified by Babangida (2021) that recruitment and selection is process where an organization take stock of their current employee and project the future need of the organization to filled in any vacancy. Furthermore, several studies revealed that manpower planning played a very significant role on improving academic staff performance in tertiary institutions, (Oforokun, 2012; Onyema, 2018 and Adekoya, 2019). So, it is against this background the study intends to assess the effects of recruitment and selection on academic staff performance at Nasarawa state university - Nigeria.

Statement of Problems

Recruitment and selection is part of manpower planning which is an essential component and determinant of academic staff performance in African higher institutions. This can be traced to the effectiveness of the recruitment and selection process. It was observed from 1980s, 1990s to date Academic staff in the Africa higher institution suffer setback due to the increase in number of student enrolment with few numbers of Academic staff. The Academic staff has a limited time to supervise student project/research work, conduct it personal research, and attend both national and international conferences. They also find it difficult to conduct practical and lectures for student with the limited time. These affect the performance of most African Academic staff (Elijah 2016).

Similarly, academic staff in Nigeria institutions and Nasarawa state were not exempted from the same fate. Apart from high number of enrolment of students, most of Nigerian intellectuals are leaving the country to go abroad due to low pay, poor motivation, inadequate or lack of equipment and working facilities, unfavorable environment etc. For example, statistics show that from 2014 to date the rate of turnover and number of academic staff that left to abroad is alarming (Chigozie, 2022). It ranges from 16.3% to 34.5% of Nigerian academic staff. The major reason responsible for the academic staff to go abroad is due to safety, poor work condition, bad leadership and good incentive by other countries. The outrageous enrolment of students in Nigerian institutions and continuous fleeing of the intellectuals to abroad has make the performance of the relative left academic staff relatively low and unimpressive. It also demoralizes effort to imparting quality education which truncate to underperformance. The low and unimpressive performance of such academic staff implies low morale and expertise while delivering lecture, weak supervision of project and practical, inability to communicate effectively, and inability to address tasks independently. Low performances of such academic staff lead to production of graduates which cannot afford to express themselves clearly write down a memo or application letter (Krishna, 2021).

Perhaps, it assumed that proper recruitment and selection of the academic staff played an integral role in improving performance. This is because if the right academic staff were recruited, select and place to fill the existing vacant can deliver up to expectation. Right placement of the academic staff to occupied the right position boost morale. Similarly, after recruitment and selection of such academic staff need to be train and retrain so as to handle and manage new equipments.

Moreover, several studies conducted on effect of recruitment and selection on performance of academic staff in tertiary institutions revealed the existence of positive relationship. This was attested by the work of Decker, (2015); Ubabuikie, (2019) and Effiong, Ekpe and Usoro, (2022) that revealed the existence of significant relationship between

recruitment and selection and performance of academic staff among tertiary institutions. Despite the existence of positive and significant relationship among such studies, the performance of academic staff in Nigerian institutions at Nasarawa state university specifically is dismally unimpressive. This might not be exempted from the fact that most of the studies have used human resource certification and human resource promotion (Decker, 2015); training, recruitment and selection (Ubabuiké, 2019) and climate balance, motivation and incentive (Effiong, Ekpe and Usoro, 2022). In addition, most of the previous studies on manpower planning and performance of academic staff of tertiary institutions were not conducted in Nasarawa state, and keffi specifically. This has created a wide gap that this study effect of recruitment and selection on the performance of academic staff of the Nasarawa state university, Nigeria intend to fill.

Research Questions

This study seeks to answer the following questions;

- i. To what extent has recruitment affected the performance of academic staff at Nasarawa state university, Nigeria
- ii. To what extent has selection affected performance of academic staff at Nasarawa state university, Nigeria

Objective of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine the effect of recruitment and selection on performance of academic staff at Nasarawa state university, Nigeria

Specifically, the study set the following objectives;

- a) To examine the effect of Recruitment on the performance of academic staff at Nasarawa state university, Nigeria
- b) To examine the effect of Selection on the performance of academic staff at Nasarawa state university, Nigeria

Research Hypotheses

The following are the alternative hypotheses that the study seeks to test;

- c) H1: Recruitment has no significant effects on the performance of academic staff at Nasarawa state university, Nigeria
- d) H2: Selection has no significant effects on the performance of academic staff at Nasarawa state university, Nigeria

Conceptual Review

Performance

Richard (2009) says that performance encompasses three specific areas of firm outcomes; financial performance (profits, return on assets, return on investment, etc.); product market performance (sales, market share, etc.) and shareholder return (total shareholder return, economic value added, etc.). Performance can be considered from two perspectives, firstly, there is the performance of the individual in question and how their personal performance is affected by the concept of employee participation. Secondly, there is the performance of the organization as a whole to consider and how this will change with varying degrees of employee participation Williamson, 2008. Also looked at performance as a particular result obtained in management, economics, marketing, etc.. that print features of competitiveness, efficiency and effectiveness of the organization and its procedural and structural components, From the above definition the authors looked at performance as a result or an outcome which is not out of place performance can also be refer to as a process that give birth to an outcome, which mean the outcome can be positive or negative depending on what took place during the process.

Measures of Performance

- a. **Productivity of employees:** In manufacturing organization productivity is measure by their revenue divided by the total number of employees. Many researchers, however, prefer to compute the natural log of revenue divided by the total number of employees (Subramony, Krause, Norton, and Burns, 2008). Williamson (2008) is of the opinion that perceptions of pay affect productivity. That is, productivity, as measured by the natural log of revenue divided by the total number of employees, increased if employees, one year earlier, had reported they felt their pay was competitive.
- b. **Sales and market share;** Sales is often used to gauge the performance of organizations. Nevertheless, several variants of sales have been utilized. Sales relative to targets is to be calculated. That is, senior management had estimated the sales target of each site, depending on the product lines, characteristics of the clientele, and other factors. To compute sales performance, actual sales was divided by target sales, and then multiplied by 100. This study showed that sites in which employees felt trusted by management experienced a sense of responsibility and accountability, which translated into improvements in this sales index (Salamon and Robinson, 2008).
- c. **Total sales growth:** Productivity can also be measure in term of total sale growth rather than merely sales, as well as market share (Gong et. al, 2009). Studies indicate that Human Relations systems that relate to productivity have been

shown to enhance performance, as measured by similar measures. These systems include extensive training, competitive pay that is contingent upon performance, career planning, performance appraisal, and participation in decision making (Gong, 2009).

- d. **Customer service;** In lieu of more objective measures of workplace performance, some researchers also assess subjective indices. One of the most common subjective indices is customer service. Customer service rates more favorably if employees feel trusted by management (Salamon and Robinson, 2008) Subjective estimates of financial performance; some researchers utilize a measure that, in essence, combines the benefits of objectives indices with the merits of subjective indices. Specifically, participants are asked to complete a series of subjective questions, which are intended to gauge objective indices. These measures have been shown to correlate appreciably with objective measures (Rhodes, Hung, Lok, Ya-Hui Lien, and Wu, 2008).
- e. **Achievement of goals;** many indices of workplace performance disregard the goals of organizations. In one year, for example, organizations might want to invest in expensive technology, to enhance productivity in the future. The profit in this year might be negligible even if the workplace fulfills its objectives. Accordingly, profit might not be a suitable measure of performance in this context. Therefore, to gauge workplace performance, the extent to which the organization has fulfilled its goals is examined. Organizations that manage errors effectively were more likely to fulfill their goals. That is, organizations were more likely to satisfy their goals, as measured by these two items, is employees communicated knowledge about errors, collaborated to resolve errors, and introduced practices that detect and manage errors expeditiously (Van Dyck, Frese, Baer, and Sonnentag, 2005).

Academic Staff Performance

Academic performance refers teaching and research activities (Ter Bogt & Scapens, 2012). To be more competitive, research is more highly valued than teaching in academic institutions. The research activities of the Academic Staff is the root cause of any issues to the society, so the publication of research is a widely accepted metric of academic performance. In contrast, publishing in low impact journals reduces the academic excellence of the researcher. Hence, the Academic Staff effectiveness can be measured by the quality information inside the classroom, students' placement, the position of the employment of graduation, research carried out, and publication in the indexed journals in the context of higher education institutions. (Harvey et,al,2010)

According to Steinberger (1993), academic performance is a multidimensional concept of academic activities and discourses related to the emotional, social, cognitive, and physical development of humans. The main objective of academic output is to prepare both Academic Staff and their students for research activities. Besides this, another objective is to prepare them for delivering the ideas and concepts of research inside a classroom along with developing new concepts. (UGC 2010) India identified the academic performance indicator (API) into three categories-(1) teaching and learning (2) co-curricular and professional development, and (3) research and academic activities. The framework highlights both activities of lecturing in classrooms and conducting research activities outside the classrooms. Research in Academic performance is concerned with academic attainment and extra-curricular achievements of students. The researcher further explained the students' academic activities include the academic ranking, graduation classes, and graduation rates of students as indicators of higher institution performance evaluation while the extra-curricular accomplishments consist of competitive roles, creativity, organizational strength, sustainability, and market share. The major objectives of any higher institutions are to teach, make active participation of the learners, produce new knowledge which is required in the society and nation, and enhance the individuals' and organizational capacity. Hilman and Abubakar (2017)

Recruitment

Internal recruitment is one in which those already member of the organization may likely be used to occupy the existing post by application. One very important fact has it that there must be a vacant post that needs to be filled. If internal applicant is qualified, he may be given the post. It can be promotion or transferring him from his current department to another where there is vacancy. Some organizations might just consider the applicant's past performance and if his records are good, the post is then given to him. To ensure workers from within helps to raise the employees' morals. When the others know that their good record can fetch them promotion and better positions, they would endeavor to show good behaviors that will help increase their productivity. Internal recruitment helps the organization to recognize and utilize the best of their staff. In this way, it fully taps the qualities of the workers (Amobi, 2019).

Internal Recruitment

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External Recruitment

Officers charged with this external recruitment, must be able to notify the prospective applicants. They need information such as the job description, job specification, the expiration of the application, the sex and where possible the salary (Obi, 2015). The sources of internal recruitment can include: advertising, educational institutions, religious and social organizations, circulars, posters, handbills and banner, labour unions, government and private employment agencies, consultancy firms etc. The type of job and work will help to determine the type of the sources of recruitment. To source for workers from outside makes it possible for an organization to get.

Selection

The selection and interviewing of applicants should not be left with the personnel officer alone. The presence of the department manager who is the line manager will determine the professional skills of the applicant's regard on the conditions and structure of the organization. The selection starts immediately the applicant starts arriving; the application reception officer is expected to go through the applications and to short-list the applicants that seated the needed criteria for interviews. In some organization, short-listed applicants are sent application forms.

The forms provide a fairly quick and systematic means of obtaining a variety of information about the applicant. Interview is an encounter with a purpose. It employs conversation which aims at bringing out attitude, gelling behavior and facts of an issue method of interviewing can be any of the following as explained by Obi single interview is a method where the candidate sit face to face with a single interview. It is a one-man interview (Obi 2015).

Key to Successful Selection of Employees

The organization must recognize that selection of employees is one of his most important tasks, so it need to insist on his recruitment efforts, hiring people with the strict qualification rigidities. Formal education, family background, religion, federal character, age and balancing of the sex equation should not be his pre-occupation. He needs people who can get the job done; self-motivated individuals who have experience and the determination to work and work to produce results, the organization should go for them. Organization must insist on hiring employees whose skills and capabilities complement existing employees. By so doing, the organization minimizes too much hiring. (Eva Yanti (2022).

Conceptual Framework

The objective of the research is to investigate the effect of recruitment and selection on performance of the academic staff of Nasarawa State Nigeria. After considering the research objectives, question, hypothesis, theories guiding the study and review of related literature, the variables of the study are identified. The framework was formed to show clearly the effect of independent variables on dependent variable. Therefore, the model is stipulated below:

Fig. 1.: The conceptual framework of te study
Source: The researchers

Empirical Review

This section will review related studies conducted by previous researcher on the variables use for this study.

Relationship between Recruitment, Selection and Staff Performance

Sohrab Hossain et al., (2015) conducted a research work on effects of recruitment and selection process on employee turnover and its consequence on organization’s profitability- A Study on Financial Sector of Bangladesh. Possessing a strong employee team, being profitable and achieving less turnover are desired by every organization. In country like Bangladesh, it is crucial to manage the recruitment and selection process properly to reduce turnover for both government and non-government sectors. The study aims at pointing out the effect of recruitment and selection

process on employee turnover and its consequence on the organization's profitability. The research has been conducted through a multiple case study method. Data has been collected with semi-structured interviews with twenty individual cases where the individuals are chosen from selected financial organizations. Analysis was done through pattern matching technique, based on the theoretical framework expected patterns were formulated and from the semi-structured interviews, empirical patterns were defined. Two propositions were proposed appropriate recruitment and selection process affects employee turnover and proper recruitment and selection affects employee turnover which increases organization's profitability. The study initiates that a small number of turnover factors can be controlled during the recruitment and selection process; thus, organization becomes capable of reducing turnover up to a definite level and this reduced turnover eventually boosts up organization profitability. Thus the study partially confirmed the first proposition and completely confirmed the second proposition.

Eva Yanti et al (2022) conducted a study on the effects of recruitment on employee performance in which they stressed that Employees are the most important part to achieve the goals of a company or organization. So that the company runs effectively and efficiently, the company needs employees who are in accordance with the principle of "the right man in the right office". To achieve the goals of the company or organization, the first step taken is to recruit prospective employees according to the qualifications of the company or organization, which will improve employee performance results while in a company or organization.

Sujeet Kumar (2014) conduct a study on recruitment and selection process in which he viewed that better recruitment and selection strategies result in improved organizational outcomes. With reference to this context, the research paper on recruitment and selection has been prepared to put a light on Recruitment and Selection process. The main objective is to identify general practices that organizations use to recruit and select employees and, to determine how the recruitment and selection practices affect organizational outcomes at Electronics Industry, In Krishna India. Successful recruitment and selection practices are key components at the entry point of human resources in any organization. The main objective of the paper is to identify general practices that organizations use to recruit and select employees. The study also focusses its attention to determine how the recruitment and selection practices affect the organizational outcomes and provide some suggestions that can help. Data analysis has been done with statistical tools like tables, graphs, pie charts, bar diagrams.

It was observed from the above study that to enhance quality organization need to recruit and select applicants with require skill needed for the job even though the study was not conducted in the polytechnic setting, it will be determine by this study whether recruitment and selection play vital role in the performance of the Academic Staff of Nasarawa State Nigeria.

Resource Base View Theory

The resource-based view (RBV) is another model or theory that focuses on the concept of sustainable competitiveness in an organization (Nalla & Varalaxmi, 2014). According to this model, companies that go a step further to develop their human resource assets will find it easier to tackle the challenge of competition. The existing rivals in the industry will find it hard to compete with the company and subsequently improve the level of performance. According to the RBV model, firms should go a step further to evaluate their workforces. By so doing, the companies will attract and retain individuals who possess the required competencies. The skills are then matched with the emerging needs or goals of the organization (Ekwoaba & Ikeje, 2015). This practice will subsequently result in a situation whereby a competitive advantage becomes the driving force in the firm.

The caliber of workers, the established relationships, and leadership practices implemented in an organization will dictate the level of performance. When HR managers identify the best approaches to strengthen their human capital resources, it will become easier to deal with the existing rivalry and eventually promote performance (Adewale & Anthonia, 2013). The use of the RBV model can transform the situation and eventually make the targeted company successful.

After hiring the right individuals, companies can go ahead to implement powerful initiatives that can promote equality and fairness. The equity approach model is one of the theories that can be used by companies to empower their employees. The theory guides companies to embrace the best policies that can result in equal opportunity (Adewale & Anthonia, 2013). Such opportunities should be considered from recruitment to retention practices. The three unique policies that have the potential to promote fairness include equal chance, access, and share. This means that workplace policies and activities should be nondiscriminatory. Fair procedures, access to adequate resources, promotions, and empowerment should be implemented in companies that want to succeed.

Hence, RBV theory makes emphasis on the need for an organization to constantly evaluate its workforce so that right and qualified applicant can be employed through effective recruitment and selection process and that equality should be observed in terms of promotion and training.

Human Capital Theory

In the eighteenth-century Adam Smith (1776) initiated an improvement in human capability that is important to production, then a term of human capital was introduced by Theodore W. Schultz (1961 published in the American Economic Review, called investment in human capital. Human capital widely used after Gary Becker won the Nobel prizes initiated “human capital theory” stated that a different level of education and training contribute to a different level of wages and salaries, the more knowledge, skill and ability, the more likely to get a better job (Blair, 2012). According to Gary Becker (1964), human capital is a physical means of production. Organizations invest in human capital via education, training, and health. Later on Thomas Davenport (1999) advanced that “the component of human capital consisted of abilities, knowledge, skill, personal talent, behavior, and effort, when those three components plus time” (p 10), he extended that 1) the knowledge included IQ, intelligence, specific and general knowledge to work. 2) Skill is expertise used in working, including the physical body, and movement of the job. 3) Talent is a personal characteristic which is innate and can be improved by development. 4) Behavior is an expression and observable behavior, norm, ethics and personal belief. 5) Effort is when people try to use their innate or personal resources including their talent, experience, knowledge and ability to work to be successful, and finally there is time.

According to Becker (1964), human capital can be accumulated in different forms of education, training, migration, and health. Through such forms, employees gain knowledge, skills and abilities in different ways. Firms invest in human capital because these firms view humans as an asset and expect that what the firm has invested will be returned and provide a positive value in the future.

The human capital theory also focuses on the development of employee in the organization looking at employee as an asset to organization that failure to develop them will lead to poor performance, but the theory failed to look at the process of recruitment and selection of employee.

Underpinning Theory.

This study will adopt “human capital theory” which stated that a different level of education and training contribute to a different level of wages and salaries, the more knowledge, skill and ability, the more likely to get a better job (Blair, 2012). According to Gary Becker (1964), human capital is a physical means of production. Organizations invest in human capital via education, training, and health. Later on Thomas Davenport (1999) advanced that “the component of human capital consisted of abilities, knowledge, skill, personal talent, behavior, and effort, when those three components plus time”. Because the theory focused on the development of employee (Academic staff) in the university looking at lecturers as assets to their organization that failure to develop them will lead to poor academic performance.

Methodology

Research Design

This study will adopt quantitative research where survey research design using 5-point Likert scale questionnaire ranging from Strongly Agree (SA) to Strongly Disagree (SD) to collect data in order to establish the effect of recruitment and selection on the performance of academic staff of Nasarawa State University, Nigeria. The target population of this study will be 737 comprises of all academic staff, cutting across all the cadre. Since the population is large, the researcher adopts Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sampling technique in which the population represented with a sample of 248 academic staff. After retrieving the completed questionnaire, the data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics and regression with the help of SPSS version 25.0.

Population of the Study

The population of this study comprised all the academic staff of Nasarawa State University which has a total number of 737 Academic Staff as at the time of this study.

Sampling Techniques: This study adopts stratified sampling technique where all the respondents were divided into strata in such a way that every respondent will belong to only one stratum that is the Academic staff will be divided based on their cadre, then simple random technique was applied in selecting 254 respondents.

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument of this study is questionnaire. Likert five point scale ranging from Strongly Agree (SA) to Strongly Disagree (SD) will be administered to the target respondents so as to obtain their view related to effect of recruitment and selection on Performance of the Academic Staff of Nasarawa State University- Nigeria.

Method of Data Collection

This study used structured questionnaire which was a close ended questionnaire administered to the respondents.

Method of Data Analysis

Data obtained from the study will be analyzed using descriptive statistics and regression analysis. The analysis was done with the aid of SPSS version 25.0. The choice of using regression analysis is to properly analyze the two hypotheses and to analyze the correlation between the variables under investigation. The model allowed the researchers to identify the effect of recruitment and selection on the performance of the academic staff of Nasarawa state university.

Pilot Test

Validity and Reliability of the Instruments

Among the criteria for evaluating instruments are validity and Reliability, Validity and Reliability are two different but closely related conditions (Zikmund, 2003). The adapted questionnaire on both endogenous and exogenous constructs is contextualized in the study areas through validity and reliability test.

Validity

Validity is defined as whether an instrument measures what it was designed to measure (Jamaludeen, 2012). There were three types of validity test. These include content, criterion and related construct validity (Ahmad, 2011). This study used content validity because it measured the degree to which the sample of the items represented the content that the instrument was designed to measure.

Some experts in the field of business administration from various universities and professional organizations validated the questionnaires where they raised their observations in which errors and deviations were checkmated and corrected.

The improved version of the questionnaire and the professional comments of the respective experts and the inputs were all incorporated into the final draft of the instrument. Thus, by this the instrument is hereby reliable, strong enough to measure what it is intended to measure.

Reliability

Praveen, Martin, John (2018) describes the reliability of the scale as to how free it is from random error. There are two frequently used indicators of the scale's reliability; test-retest reliability and internal consistency (Praveen, 2008; Jamaludeen, 2012). Repeatability can be assessed using a test-retest method which involves administering the same scale or measures to the same respondents at two separate times in order to test for stability in the model (Ahmad, 2011). If the measure is stable over the period, the result of the test-retest should be similar and that was achieved through pilot study.

The study used both the internal consistency reliability test using Cronbach alpha and test-retest reliability through pilot study. The pilot study replicated with modifications and the measures or instruments other researchers have used in their previous studies. Therefore, the pilot study was essential to determine the understanding ability of the survey instrument. More importantly, a pilot test conducted ensured that the questions are understandable and present accurate portrayal of the situation.

The results from the pilot testing helped in the determination of the reliability of the survey instrument and in the identification of items on the scales that would need to be deleted. Extensive piloting of the survey instrument was essential when testing whether the instrument is capable of generating the required responses from the respondents (Smith, 2011). Moreover, the pilot test presented many benefits for the researcher as it explored particular issues that may potentially have an incompatible impact on the survey results such as the appropriateness of questions to the target population. Therefore, it tested the correctness of the instrument measured as to whether all the respondents in the pilot sample were able to follow the directions as indicated. It also provided better information on whether the type of survey is effective in fulfilling the purpose of the study, and save financial resources. Accordingly, for this study, sixty (60) questionnaires were distributed in order to refine the survey instrument prior to the actual survey administration.

Internal Consistency Reliability (Pilot Test) Results

S/N	Variables	Cronbach Alpha	No of Items
1	Recruitment	0.816	6
2	Selection	0.752	6
3	Academic Staff Performance	0.800	4

Source: SPSS Version 23 output, 2022

Traditionally, “Cronbach’s alpha” is used to measure internal consistency reliability in social science research as shown in table above. Previous literature has suggested the use of “Composite Reliability” as a replacement (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988; Hair Sarstedt, Ringle & Mena, 2019). Composite reliability should be 0.70 or higher. If it is an exploratory research, 0.6 or higher is acceptable (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988). From table above, such values of Cronbach alpha are shown to be larger than 0.70, so high levels of internal consistency reliability have been demonstrated among all the latent variables. Therefore, internal consistency reliability is achieved based on the pilot data obtained.

Appendix I:

Table for Determining Sample of a Finite Population
Krejcie and Morgan Table

<i>N</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>S</i>
10	10	220	140	1200	291
15	14	230	144	1300	297
20	19	240	148	1400	302
25	24	250	152	1500	306
30	28	260	155	1600	310
35	32	270	159	1700	313
40	36	280	162	1800	317
45	40	290	165	1900	320
50	44	300	169	2000	322
55	48	320	175	2200	327
60	52	340	181	2400	331
65	56	360	186	2600	335
70	59	380	191	2800	338
75	63	400	196	3000	341
80	66	420	201	3500	346
85	70	440	205	4000	351
90	73	460	210	4500	354
95	76	480	214	5000	357
100	80	500	217	6000	361
110	86	550	226	7000	364
120	92	600	234	8000	367
130	97	650	242	9000	368
140	103	700	248	10000	370
150	108	750	254	15000	375
160	113	800	260	20000	377
170	118	850	265	30000	379
180	123	900	269	40000	380
190	127	950	274	50000	381
200	132	1000	278	75000	382
210	136	1100	285	100000	384

Note.—*N* is population size. *S* is sample size.

Source: Krejcie & Morgan, 1970

CONCLUSION

Being a pilot study, the researchers discussed the research aim and objectives, hypothesis, the methodology and rationale behind the study. It outlined the sampling design, methods and strategy of data collection. The researchers also highlighted the instrument used for measurement of the variables for the pilot study as well as the validity and reliability of the instrument. Furthermore, the result of the reliability test for the study is thereafter presented. Finally, the researchers described the method of data analysis that was used for this study.

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